

Chelating N-ligands and their Transition Metal Complexes. Part III. Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of *vic*-oxime Imines

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Several *vic*-oxime-imines have been prepared and their UV absorption spectra in methanol and alkali solutions are investigated.

vic-Oxime imines having the structural configuration $\begin{array}{c} -C=N- \\ | \\ -C=NOH \end{array}$ are expected to be closely related to *vic*-dioxime and *vic*-oxime hydrazones. Hence, in continuation of our studies on N-ligands derived from 1,2-diketones and related substances^{1,2}, we have prepared a series of *vic* oxime-imines. The present paper deals with the preparation and ultra-violet absorption spectra of the Schiff bases (I) obtained from the derivatives of 2,3-dioxobutyramide-2-oxime and primary amines. These oximeimines are considered to have preferentially the anti-configuration (II) similar to the structure suggested for the dioximes obtained from $COCH_2$ compounds³.

(I)

(II)

The Ultra-violet absorption spectra (λ_{max} and E_m) of these Schiff bases (I) in methanol and alkali solutions are presented in Table I.

The intense absorption band (K) at 223-33 $m\mu$ observed in the spectra of these Schiff bases (I) in methanol is considered to be a $\pi \leftrightarrow \pi^*$ transition and is attributed to the crossed conjugated system,

Since the absorption bands of 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime¹ and its oxime and benzylimine in alcohol are at 236-38 $m\mu$, 236-38 $m\mu$ and 226 $m\mu$ respectively, the replacement of the conjugated carbonyl or oxime group by the conjugated imine group causes a

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2. A. M. Talati and P. M. Desai *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 677.

3. M. Ishidate, *Mikrochim. Acta.*, 1938, **3**, 203.

blue shift of about 10-12 $m\mu$. Hence it is suggested that the replacement of conjugated $>C=O$ by conjugated $>C=N$ -weakens conjugation. Replacement of CH_2 by OH or Ph into conjugated $>C=N-X$ ($X=CH_2$, OH or Ph) group causes a red shift of the band by 10-12 $m\mu$ and 5-6 $m\mu$ respectively. If the Ph ring is insulated from or is at right angle to the absorbing conjugated system, no shift of the band will be observed. On the other hand, if the Ph ring is coplanar with the crossed conjugated system, a red shift due to Ph group will be observed, the shift being greater than that due to OH group. Hence, in the present case the coplanarity of the phenyl ring with the remaining conjugated system appears to be strained. The effect of a para-substituent in the phenyl ring on the K-band also leads to a similar conclusion.

TABLE I
UV absorption spectra of vic-oxime-imines

Schiff bases (I) where Sr. R= No.	X=	in MeOH				in NaOH			
		λ_{max} $m\mu$	E_m	λ_{max} $m\mu$	E_m	λ_{max} $m\mu$	E_m	λ_{max} $m\mu$	E_m
1. C_6H_5	C_6H_5NH	231-32	24450	—	—	258	11720	290-92	13520
2. C_6H_5	$o-CH_3C_6H_4NH$	223	18970	—	—	256	13530	276	13770
3. C_6H_5	$o-ClC_6H_4NH$	—	—	274-78	7630	256	13500	290	15720
4. $C_6H_5CH_2$	C_6H_5NH	226	14660	270-72	12560	—	—	268-70	14690
5. $C_6H_5CH_2$	$o-CH_3C_6H_4NH$	—	—	272-74	14410	—	—	270	14180
6. $C_6H_5CH_2$	$o-ClC_6H_4NH$	—	—	276	21750	—	—	270	16570
7. $p-CH_3C_6H_4$	C_6H_5NH	232-33	25310	—	—	256-62	13050	286-88	14730
8. $p-CH_3C_6H_4$	$o-CH_3C_6H_4NH$	—	—	—	—	—	—	280	12920
9. $p-CH_3C_6H_4$	$o-ClC_6H_4NH$	—	—	277	7870	258-60	11960	290	15020

Introduction of ortho-substituents (Cl, CH_3) in the anilide ring system leads to a blue shift in the spectra of these Schiff bases and may be attributed to the side chain effect on the absorbing system. The results indicate the coplanarity of the anilide ring system with the absorbing conjugated system.

The second band (X) is observed at 270-78 $m\mu$ in some of these spectra in methanol and is attributed to the ionic tautomer of the conjugated oxime in these compounds. It is seen that the intensity of the band in the case of benzylimine Schiff bases is much greater than that of the band for other Schiff bases.

The K-band is observed at 256-62 $m\mu$ region in the spectra of these Schiff bases in alkali solutions, intensity of the band being reduced to almost half the intensity of the band in alcoholic solution.

The insulation of the Ph ring from the conjugated imine group by CH_2 has a marked influence on the X-band in the spectra of these Schiff bases in alkali solutions. Thus a little blue shift is observed when the X-band in alkali solution is compared with the corresponding band in alcoholic solution. On the other hand, when Ph ring is not insulated, there is a marked red shift when the X-band in alkali solution is compared with the corresponding band in alcoholic solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Schiff bases from N-aryl 2,3-dioxobutyramide 2-oxime. N-aryl 2,3-dioxobutyramide 2-oxime (0.1 mole) and primary amine (0.1 mole) dissolved separately in alcohol were mixed, warmed a little and kept at room temperature. The crystalline product obtained was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol. The products obtained together with their colour, m p. and analysis (micro) are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Schiff bases from N-aryl 2,3-dioxobutyramide 2-oxime

No.	Schiff bases (I) where	R=	X=	Colour	M. P. °C	% N found	% N reqd.
1.		C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ NH	White	187	15.38	14.94
2.		C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ NH	White	155	13.99	14.21
3.		C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ NH	White	160	13.67	13.31
4.		C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₆ H ₅ NH	Red	137	14.60	14.23
5.		C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ NH	Red	135	14.13	13.59
6.		C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ NH	Red	145	12.36	12.74
7.		<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅ NH	White	163	13.88	14.23
8.		<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ NH	White	164	13.39	13.58
9.		<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ NH	White	160	12.53	12.74

UV absorption spectra in methanol and sodium hydroxide solutions were investigated with a Beckman model DU Spectrophotometer, using matched 1 cm. quartz cells.

Thanks are due to Prof. S. M. Sethna for his keen interest in the work and to Dr. S. S. Lele for micro-analysis (%N) of the samples.

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Received, May 2, 1967.